

Impact of Social Media Misinformation on Credibility-based Disengagement from Broadcast Media: Role of Media Literacy in Youth

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Abstract

The reliance on social media (SM) for information by the youth/teenagers is increasing day by day on platforms such as Facebook, Instagram, TikTok, YouTube and X (formerly Twitter), where misleading information is circulating rapidly and affects their perceptions of traditional journalism. This study investigates the impact of SM misinformation on youth disengagement from broadcast media, focusing on the mediating role of perceived credibility and the moderating role of media literacy. Implementing the media effects theory and Mediatization theory, this study proposes that misinformation negatively influences the youth perception about broadcast media, which in turn contributes to disengagement from television and radio news. This research also investigates whether media literacy weakens the negative effects of misinformation on credibility.

A quantitative cross-sectional survey was designed using a Likert scale instrument; data were collected from people aged 15-30 across Islamabad and Rawalpindi. The survey uses online Google Form questionnaires. Pilot testing shows the reliability and validity of the scales. Analysis was conducted using SPSS, including descriptive, correlation and multiple regression analyses.

Findings demonstrate that exposure to misinformation significantly reduces the youth perception of credibility of broadcast media and raises their disengagement. Credibility mediates the relationship between misinformation and disengagement, supporting the purpose theoretical framework. Media literacy moderates the connection between misinformation and credibility, indicating that the youth with a high level of literacy are less affected by the misleading or false information content online.

The conclusions highlight the requirement for higher media literacy programs among youth and powerful broadcast media credibility strategies to counter the increasing influence of misinformation on youth. The study also recommended future research directions.

INTRODUCTION

In the modern digital world, the rapid growth of various SM (SM) platforms has transformed the way audiences consume information. SM has become the main source of information for

young people. Globally, these platforms, such as Facebook, Instagram, TikTok, YouTube and X, have become the leading resources among youngsters, allowing users to share, receive, and comment on news in the form of video, image, or meme. Traditional broadcast media such as television and Radio were once the predominant source of news, but as the young generations spend most of their time on SM, they are becoming less interested in TV news, as many depend on short information in SM or influencer content to learn more about what is happening around the world. Radio, Television, and newspapers, which are becoming obsolete due to the intense use of SM platforms, have much higher editorial oversight and regulation mechanisms. Unlike SM, which operates in a largely unregulated domain, that open and unregulated environment has made SM a fertile ground for the spread of misinformation and fake news. Moreover, the SM algorithms show more content based on engagement rather than accuracy. As a result, the young generation is often more vulnerable to biased or distorted views of events, shaping their attitudes towards journalism and their opinions.

In this circumstance, Media literacy becomes a key factor, as it has the capacity to analyse, access, evaluate, and critically create media. Teenagers can identify misinformation better, who are more media literate can identify misinformation better and can verify facts and grasp the motive behind the online content. Like the teenager in Norway, they are more literate and go towards verifying if they come across any misinformation. (Selnes, 2023) This awareness reduces the negative impact of misinformation and helps them make more informed choices. Therefore, media literacy can act as a moderating factor in how misinformation or fake news influences disengagement from broadcast media.

The perceived credibility of broadcast media also plays an important role. At the same time, if the teenager still believes that the broadcast media is reliable and ethical, this can decrease the influence of the misinformation, credibility may work as a shield, and their trust in credible broadcast media may prevent whole disengagement. This shows how media credibility can serve as a mediating factor in a relationship. Apprehending these relationships is not only important for academic research but also for media organizations and educators. If the false information uninterruptedly weakens the connection between the young audience and credible journalism, the future of informed citizens could be at risk.

In recent years, the global information landscape has changed rapidly due to the rise of digital media platforms. Teenagers are particularly the most active users of these platforms, such as Instagram, TikTok, Facebook, YouTube, and X (formerly Twitter). According to Selnes (2023) SM has become the primary place where the young audience faces news content, often in short,

visually compelling formats. However, this change has also made them more vulnerable to disinformation and misinformation, which is continuously circulating across these platforms without any restrictions or policies.

The spread of false misinformation or misleading content without appropriate verification has emerged as a very serious issue globally. Diaz Ruiz (2023) Notes that digital platforms have created an information market where veracity is replaced by attention, emotional reaction, and engagement. As a result, the audience, particularly teenagers, is repeatedly vulnerable to manipulated stories and fabricated information, which shapes their perceptions of current events. This condition has a feeble trust in traditional sources of news like TV and Radio, which were once considered reliable and professional.

Internationally, many studies have shown that misinformation can lead to news fatigue and disengagement when audiences face constant exposure to false or contradictory information; they often choose to avoid news altogether (Selnes, 2023). Wendt, Naderer, Bachl, and Rieger (2023) Argue that this vogue is especially strong among adolescents who lack the necessary media literacy expertise to critically evaluate online content. The content that appears popular or emotionally charged on SM is mostly shared and believed, even if it's false, and if these patterns continue, young people become disconnected from broadcast media that emphasize factual reporting and editorial standards.

In Pakistan, similar patterns can also be observed. A large amount of the Pakistani young generation mostly relies on digital media for news about social issues, political matters, and for entertainment purposes. A recent report by the local media research organization shows that almost 77% of young Pakistanis use online platforms for news and information purposes, often trusting viral posts or favorite influencers' more than professional journalists (Abbasi, 2020).

In this context the media literacy plays an important role in helping users to differentiate between credible and unreliable source content. Media literacy is the ability to access, understand, analyze, and evaluate media messages critically (Wendt et al., 2023). An individual with higher media literacy can identify false information, biased content, verify the facts, and make more informed decisions about what to believe. And share this way, media literacy acts as a Moderating factor between exposure to misinformation and disengagement from broadcast media. At the same time, the perceived credibility of broadcast media remains an important variable. Schulz, Fletcher, and Nielsen (2022) found that even though the young generation consumes news intensively through SM, they still believe that traditional news organizations are more trustworthy and professional. Ehrlén et al. (2023) reported that the user's trust in the

broadcast media can help counteract the negative influences of online misinformation. Therefore, if the traditional media maintain strong editorial and ethical standards, they may continue playing the mediating role that minimizes the negative effects of misinformation/disinformation on audience behavior.

However, when traditional media lose credibility due to political bias, competition, rivalry between media houses, and outdated formats, youth may completely turn towards SM for information. This leads to a process of disengagement, where misinformation replaces verified information as the main influence on public opinion. Till (2020) described this process as “reflexive control” of the audience through propaganda and mediated reality, where exposure to manipulated content slowly shapes individuals' perception of truth.

In short, the background of this study shows that misinformation on SM is not only Pakistan's problem, but also a global issue, which also causes a significant challenge in Pakistan, where the usage of SM among youth is very high, and the media literacy is very low compared to other nations of the globe. Misinformation shapes their worldview and reduces trust in broadcast media. Increasing the media literacy and credibility of traditional news outlets can help regain the trust and engagement of young audiences. This research, therefore, seeks to explore how misinformation affects youth disengagement from broadcast media and how media literacy and their credibility interact within this relationship.

Problem Statement: The rise of digital media platforms such as TikTok, Instagram, YouTube, and X (formerly Twitter) has entirely transformed how youth access and interpret news. These platforms have made information available rapidly and entertainingly, but have made it extremely difficult to separate facts from opinions. A study shows that 77% of Pakistani teenagers mostly rely on SM for their daily information about the current situation. (Abbasi, 2020). This trend created a very concerning situation when young users consume unverified, misleading, or false information online; they began to lose trust in reliable broadcast journalism.

Misinformation spreads extremely fast on digital media platforms because the content is for engagement and driven by algorithms rather than accuracy (Diaz Ruiz, 2023). Teenagers are more vulnerable to misinformation because they lack the ability to distinguish between a credible source and an unverified source. Due to lower media literacy, they are less motivated to check the authenticity of what they see or hear on SM platforms (Wendt et al., 2023). And this frequent repetition of exposure to misleading news or confusing information can lead to

disengagement or news avoidance, where the young generation stops believing in traditional broadcast media such as TV and Radio (Selnes, 2023)

In Pakistan, this disengagement is becoming visible through the declining youth audience of TV news and increasing dependence on influencers and reels, YouTube shorts, and TikTok videos for information. If this trend grows continuously, credible journalism may lose its influence among the young generation, which increases the risk of false information reshaping public opinion more critically (Wendt et al., 2023). Meanwhile, the credibility of broadcast media can moderate the negative impact of misinformation by rebuilding users' trust. (Ehrlén et al., 2023; Schulz et al., 2022).

Therefore, the central problem is: *How does exposure to misinformation on SM influence teenagers' disengagement from broadcast media, and what roles do media literacy and perceived broadcast media credibility play in this relation*

Purpose of the study: Examining how exposure to misinformation on SM influences young generation disengagement from broadcast media and to identify the role of media literacy and perceived credibility of broadcast media in this relationship. With the increasing growth of SM platforms, they have become the main space where young users access and engage with news (Selnes, 2023). However, this shift to digitalization increases the teens' exposure to misleading information (Diaz Ruiz, 2023). As a result, the young generation starts questioning the credibility of traditional media and considers it biased and supports favoritism.

Research Objectives: The main point of this research is to explain how the growing existence of misinformation on SM sites shapes the way youngsters in Pakistan engage or disengage with traditional broadcast media. To achieve this, the study is guided by the following specific objective.

- To examine the extent of youth exposure to misinformation on SM platforms and identify the type of misleading content that most often influences their opinions and behavior.
- To analyze how exposure to misinformation affects the youth's interest, trust, and involvement in traditional broadcast media.
- To assess the moderating role of media literacy
- To provide recommendations for media institutions and news outlets

These objectives will not only help to understand the impact of misinformation but also show the influence of media literacy and institutional credibility. Together, they give a framework

for understanding how the new generation of Pakistan uses media and how they understand the trusted and untrusted information on SM platforms.

Significance: This study holds academic and practical importance in understanding how misleading information on SM affects the media usage of youth in Pakistan. In a civilization where data is produced and consumed rapidly, the young generation is constantly exposed to unverified content that influences their attitude towards journalism and trust. As (Selnes, 2023) Explain that teenagers are no longer the passive consumers of media; instead, they purposely select, interpret, and share informative news based on what appears on their SM feeds. This is empowering youth, but also exposes them to misleading, false information that shapes their view.

From an academic perspective, this research contributes to the growing body of literature on digital misinformation, media literacy, and faith in journalism; also, it extends the previous research (Wendt et al., 2023). By giving direct attention to a developing country like Pakistan, where information through SM penetration is very high compared to uneven media literacy. By testing the mediating and moderating effects of perceived credibility of broadcast media and media literacy, this study offers a deeper understanding of how these factors interact within the framework of media effects and audience engagement.

Practically, the findings will help media institutes and organizations to design strategies to regain youth engagement, and broadcast media will use the findings to improve the credibility and traditional media presentation. For policymakers, this study may guide initiatives to promote responsible digital communication and counter the increasing spread of misinformation online.

Finally, this study is significant because it addresses a currently processing social issue, “the growing gap between the young generation and traditional journalism.” If the misleading information continues to govern the information space, it can slowly weaken the role of credible media in shaping informed citizens and democratic participation (Ehrlén et al., 2023; Schulz et al., 2022).

Scope: The focus of this research is to understand how misinformation on SM platforms changes the youth perception about broadcast media and influences their behavior, thought, opinion, and thinking capabilities in the context of Pakistan, and aims to identify the mediating effects of perceived broadcast media credibility and the moderating mission of media literacy within this relationship. It is limited to SM platforms like Facebook, Instagram, TikTok, YouTube, and X (formerly Twitter). It is targeting young generation Z

Literature Review

The literature reviews identify the gap that is still present and help to provide more information about what is already known to the research. The literature review helps find what is already known about the research topic (Creswell, 2018). By analyzing different local and international studies, this part builds the theoretical and empirical ground for the current research.

This conversation begins with an overview of the global trend of misinformation and digital media use, showing how SM platforms have transformed the news consumption patterns (Diaz Ruiz, 2023; Selnes, 2023). It then checks how media literacy functions as a protective skill or education that enables the user to critically evaluate the online news/information (Wendt et al., 2023). The next part will explore the perception of how credibility in traditional journalism, broadcast media and how trust or distrust affects the user audience engagement (Ehrlén et al., 2023; Schulz et al., 2022)

It also reviews the theoretical approaches, especially the Mediatization theory and Media-effects Framework, to explain how media shape/change behavior and attitude. This viewpoint gives the conceptual foundation for understanding the relationship between misinformation, credibility, and literacy in this study.

By blending past research, literature, and theoretical insights. This study aims to clarify the research gap, while most of the work has been done in the Western context. Little is known about how this dynamic works within the Pakistani young generation. Therefore, the review connects the local context and international findings to support the development of a hypothesis and the conceptual framework presented earlier.

Key Terms and Variable Discussion

For conceptual clarity, we have to understand these four core concepts.

Misinformation on SM as an Independent Variable: Misinformation means the false or misleading information shared without verifying its authenticity. On SM, misinformation spread rapidly through generated content, emotional posts, videos, and algorithmic magnification (Diaz Ruiz, 2023). Mostly, Teenagers encounter these kinds of misleading information on social platforms such as TikTok, Facebook, X (formerly Twitter), Instagram, and YouTube, which affects how they perceive news and journalism (Selnes, 2023). Researchers explore, and studies have found that many teen SM users often struggle to verify online news, which leads to confusion and distrust in mainstream media (Till, 2020).

Perceived Credibility of Broadcast Media as Mediator: Credibility refers to the extent to which the user believes that traditional broadcast media news organizations are accurate,

trustworthy, and fair (Schulz et al., 2022). When the audiences believe that the broadcast media is credible, they are more likely to rely on it even when confronted with misleading information on online platforms. Low perceived credibility weakens the audience's trust and loyalty. In this study, perceived credibility acts as a mediator, which mediates the correlation between misinformation and disengagement (Schulz et al., 2022)

Media Literacy (Moderating Moderator): Media literacy is the ability to access, analyze, evaluate, and think about media messages critically. It makes any individual make a difference between reliable and unreliable information sources (Wendt et al., 2023). Within this study, media literacy works as a moderator which moderates the effects of misinformation on perceived credibility. Higher levels of media literacy enable the user to identify biased, false, and manipulated information, which reduces the negative impact/influence of the information, so the credibility of broadcast media is less harmed, but the youth with less media literacy are more affected by the misinformation.

Youth disengagement from broadcast media as a Dependent variable: The disengagement occurs when the audience loses interest, and the interest weakens by losing trust in connection with broadcast media such as radio and television or the extreme use of SM (Selnes, 2023) Observe that the teen or young generation prefers interactive engagement, such as visually rich and personalized content, which the SM platform provides. As a result, their attention from broadcast journalism moves toward online platforms for staying informed. This research theorizes disengagement as both attitudinal and behavioral withdrawal from broadcast media.

Previous Studies

Empirical research provides the measurable documentation for understanding how misleading information, media literacy, and credibility influence user disengagement. Below are the studies that form the empirical foundation for the current study and have tested the related framework through quantitative or mixed-method approaches in the field of digital and broadcast media.

Fake news on SM and teen disengagement: Selnes (2023) explored how exposure to fake news on SM contributes to teen disengagement from traditional broadcast media. This study surveyed 400 teenagers and found that most of them are continuously exposed to misinformation in the form of online content, which led to a decline in their trust in traditional journalism and reduced attention to TV news. She figured out that SM promotes selected content that the young generation relies on, which is algorithmically recommended instead of journalistically verified. This study provides the empirical base for the dependent variable –

teen/youth disengagement- and directly supports the current research's main focus on misinformation's behavioral consequences.

Media literacy as a protective factor: Wendt et al. (2023) conducted a cross-country verification study to understand the role of media literacy among teenagers and young adults. The research used a structured questionnaire to measure abilities like verification skills, source evaluation, and critical thinking. The results show that people with higher media literacy have low belief in misinformation and high trust in credible media sources. This study empirically supports media literacy as a mediating variable, suggesting that it can reduce the effects of misinformation.

Credibility and news Engagement: Schulz et al. (2022) investigated how news knowledge and credibility perceptions shaped digital media use across five countries, using comparative survey data. They found that users with high knowledge of the news process, meaning how the news is produced, and who have strong trust in media institutions, were less likely to rely only on news from SM platforms. This research empirically tested the credibility as a moderating variable. This shows that when the broadcast media is believed to be trustworthy, the audience remains more engaged despite exposure to digital media.

Credibility and news Engagement: Diaz Ruiz (2023) assumed a market-shaping perspective to understand the misleading information's broader social and institutional contextual impact. With a multimethod approach, including content analysis and survey data, the research shows that misinformation changes/reshapes media ecosystems by creating chaos, doubt, and polarization. This study empirically supported that the idea of misinformation functions as an independent variable, which affects both individual and institutional behavior. Its findings validate that the misinformation is the main predictor in the present research framework.

Confusing content and Media trust: Ehrlén et al. (2023) analyzed how the young generation grasps confusing or mixed-content platforms, such as digital media platforms. Collecting data from different European countries, they found that exposure to misleading, conflicting, and unverified information reduced the trust in both broadcast and digital media. This study's findings empirically join the exposure to misinformation and perceived trust and confusion, strengthening the idea that credibility plays an important role in shaping the behaviour of youth towards engagement.

Propaganda, Reflexive control and reality construction: Till (2020) Studied how reflexive control and propaganda shape public understanding of truth in mediated surroundings. Using interviews and survey-based methods, the study finds that continuous exposure to misleading

information fosters negativity toward institutional news. This study supports the psychological and cognitive procedures of misinformation spread and provides support for the cognitive approach based on this study's theoretical framework.

Background of the Framework

Many previous studies have developed a framework that clarifies the connection between misinformation, perceived media credibility, Media literacy, and audience engagement. While these models provide a beneficial insight into audience behavior in the digital era, very few have investigated how these constructs interact with each other, especially among the young generation in a developing media environment where media literacy is low.

Selnes (2023) introduce a conceptual framework demonstrating how misinformation on SM drives youth disengagement from broadcast media by weakening trust and belief. Wendt et al. (2023) presented that media literacy is a moderating variable and displayed that higher media literacy levels weaken the negative impact of misleading information and increase the audience's skill to verify credible sources. In a similar context, (Schulz et al., 2022) highlighted perceived credibility as a key mediating factor that impacts online information, content, and news on audience reliance on SM vs professional journalism. However, (Till, 2020) and (Ehrlén et al., 2023) linked regular exposure to misinformation, manipulated and conflicted content, with burnout, and weakens the trust in the traditional journalism narrative. Studies further show that youngsters are more vulnerable to false information because of their high exposure to algorithm-driven content (Selnes, 2023). When the misinformation becomes common and compelling, it undermines the perceived credibility of broadcast media, making youngster more doubtful toward radio and TV news (Schulz et al., 2022)

However, previous studies usually examined these constructs in isolation; for instance, they focused on one variable, either misinformation and engagement or literacy and credibility. No thorough empirical model has yet integrated all four constructs within a single framework or tested in a low media literacy environment or in a South Asian context.

The present study is based on these earlier frameworks by suggesting an integrated model in which (independent variable) misinformation on SM influences teen disengagement from broadcast media (dependent variable), mediated by perceived credibility of broadcast media, and moderated by Media Literacy. This integrated framework not only combines prior existing theoretical approaches but also contextualizes them within Pakistan's fast-evolving digital media environment. The current framework of this study gives a comprehensive model based on both Mediatization Theory and Media Effects Theory. It catches structural and

psychological, and perceptual factors shaping youth news behavior in a modern digitalized society. The model suggests misinformation impact is mediated through credibility and moderated by media literacy, forming the foundation for the study's hypotheses and empirical testing.

Conceptualizing the Framework: Based on above, the following research framework has been developed to understand the relationship among misinformation on SM, perceived credibility of broadcast media, media literacy and the teen disengagement from the broadcast media. This framework unifies (Schulz et al., 2022; Selnes, 2023; Wendt et al., 2023), stretching their models by combining the mediating and moderating processes into a single structure relevant to the Pakistani context.

Figure 1: Conceptual framework of the study

As shown in Figure 1, the framework addresses how misinformation on SM (Independent variable) influences youth disengagement from broadcast media (Dependent variable). This relationship is predicted to be both direct and indirect, with perceived credibility of broadcast media serving as a mediating factor. Moreover, Media literacy is situated as a moderating variable that can either weaken or strengthen this effect, depending on the Consumer education level or knowledge.

Research Methodology

This section provides the methodological framework developed for this current study, explaining how the study was designed, conducted, and analyzed to reach its objective. The methodology ensures that all research steps are logically aligned with the study purpose to understand the impact of misinformation in SM on teen disengagement from broadcast media, regarding the mediating role of broadcast media credibility and the moderating role of literacy. The section discusses the study type, design, procedure, model, instrument, population, sampling, and analysis technique used to check the proposed hypotheses. The methodological framework is based on quantitative methods, understanding measurable variables, statistical

analysis, and objective analysis of results. A survey-based method using a structured questionnaire was selected as it allows the collection of quantifiable data from a large number of young people. Enabling the research to verify all the variables. Moreover, this section eventually provides a systematic description of how the data were gathered and analysed to validate the conceptual model presented.

Nature of the Study

The current study is causal and explanatory in nature. A causal study determines cause and effect relationships between variables, whereas an explanatory study further identifies the mechanisms and contextual factors to understand how and why these relationships occur (Creswell, 2018).

In the current study, the main focus is to understand how the misinformation on SM influences teenagers' disengagement from broadcast media and to explain the roles of media literacy and broadcast media credibility within that relationship. This study supposes that the exposure to misinformation (Independent variable) has direct and indirect effects on the disengagement (Dependent variable), which is mediated by media credibility and moderated by literacy.

This study assumes a quantitative method, which allows for testing of hypotheses extracted from the conceptual framework presented above. A survey questionnaire was used to gather responses from the teenagers of the selected population. Quantitative methods are suitable because they enable measurement of a constructed variable using an established scale, ensuring validity and reliable results (Bryman, 2016).

The casual and explanatory design agrees with the study's theoretical grounds i.e. Mediatization theory and Media Effects Theory, both of which focus on the measurable influence of media exposure on user attitudes and behaviors. With this design, the study not only detects the relationship among variables but also explains the process through which misleading/false information shapes the young generation's media usage.

Research Design

This study adopts a quantitative, cross-sectional research design. A cross-sectional design collects data from respondents in a one-way manner (Creswell, 2018). The study design is aligned because the focus is to analyze the current impact rather than monitoring behavioral changes over a long period of time.

This allows the researcher to statistically test the cause-and-effect relationship. Data is gathered through the survey questionnaire form valid and reliable scales identified in the previous studies (Diaz Ruiz, 2023; Schulz et al., 2022; Wendt et al., 2023).

The present design therefore ensures that the analysis remains both empirically testable and time-bound, allowing clear measurement of variable relationships within statistical procedures like as correlation and regression.

Instruments and Scales

The main instrument used for data collection in this study was a structured, self-administered questionnaire, designed to measure all the variables included in the framework. These are developed based on a validated scale derived from prior published studies to ensure all variables are measured and established according to academic standards. The instruments comprised four main sections, each matching one of the variables. All items are measured by a five-point Likert scale from 1= strongly Disagree to 5= strongly Agree, a scale mostly used for evaluating attitudes, perceptions, and behavioural practices.(Bryman, 2016).

Construction of Questionnaire.

The questionnaire was structurally designed using a five-point Likert scale. The opening part gathered necessary demographic information about the participants, including age, gender, education level, and the frequency of SM use. These variables helped the findings and ensured that the sample represented the target population of youth between the ages of 15-30 years

Measurement Scales:

Items measuring exposure to misinformation were derived from (Diaz Ruiz, 2023; Selnes, 2023; Till, 2020). These items evaluated respondents' experiences with false information, their struggle to verify online content, and perceptions of doubtful news circulating on SM. Media literacy items were derived from the cross-validated scale created by (Wendt et al., 2023). These items measure the ability of the respondents to evaluate content credibility, identify bias, false content, and verify information, and understand how social platforms influence. Credibility items are adopted from the (Schulz et al., 2022). Their statements measured trust in broadcast media, perception of reliability, accuracy, and fairness. Disengagement items were adapted from (Selnes, 2023). She examined teen disengagement, avoidance in the context of SM use, and exposure to misinformation.

Validation of the instrument

To confirm the content validity, the questionnaire was reviewed by a subject research professor from the area of media studies. A pilot test with 20 adolescents was conducted to refine item clarity and reliability. Needed modifications were made before the final administration of the instrument.

Pilot Study: A pilot study was conducted to explore the instrument's clarity, validity, and internal consistency before the final survey started. The pilot used to identify unclear wording, response time check, and measure the reliability of each construct. A sample of 20 young people aged 15-30 from the urban School/College/University (Rawalpindi and Islamabad) participated in the pilot. It has the same questionnaire structure as the final instruments, items for misinformation, media literacy, perceived broadcast credibility, and disengagement. The survey was distributed online, and participants were given standard instructions.

Content Validity: Before the pilot, the instruments were reviewed by the media studies faculty members for content evaluation and alignment with the constructs. The pilot project was modified according to the feedback for more accurate responses.

Population and Sampling: The population for this study consists of the young generation between the ages of 15-30 who consistently use SM and are potential consumers of traditional broadcast media news in Pakistan. This age group is the active user of SM and most exposed to SM misinformation, and can likely disengage from broadcast media, as shown in the fresh research. (Ehrlén et al., 2023; Selnes, 2023).

The population of this study can be defined as: All Pakistani youth between the ages of 15-30 years old are enrolled in school, college, and at the university level, in urban areas, and spend 2-6 hours on SM platforms such as TikTok, Instagram, YouTube, and Facebook. These parameters for population were selected to align with the objective of the study: exposure to misinformation, media literacy, and disengagement.

Target Population: The target population for the current study designates a more accessible and practical part of the total population that includes the young generation or students aged 15-30 enrolled in secondary, higher school, or university students in an urban city of Pakistan, Such as Rawalpindi, Islamabad. This group is easily reachable and is the highest SM user among youth.

Sampling: A non-probability convenience sampling technique is used in the present study. It is the most suitable sampling approach as the participants are selected based on their easy accessibility and already available participants (Bryman, 2016). The students who participated in this research were approached using institutional WhatsApp groups and Google Forms. The total sample size for this study was decided using the recommendation of (Krejcie & Morgan, 1970). They suggest a minimum scale of 384 for a population of above 100,000. However, for MS quantitative research sample size range of 250 to 300 respondents is usually considered sufficient for regression analysis and mediation-moderation testing. (Creswell, 2018). So, for

this study, a final sample of 300 respondents was targeted. This sample was distributed across two cities to evaluate diversity in exposure and media habits.

Data Analysis Technique

The data was analyzed using quantitative statistical techniques in SPSS.

Pearson's correlation was used to assess the power and guidance of the linear relationship between the continuous variables, such as misinformation, media literacy, and disengagement.

The evaluation provided the initial proof of associations that support the hypotheses.

Regression was employed to test the direct effect between variable that helped to understand the predictive power of all the independent variables. Mediation analysis explains whether Perceived media credibility mediates the relationship between misinformation and teen disengagement. Moderating analysis performed using a process macro to test does Media literacy moderates the effect of misinformation on disengagement. It tells whether the credibility weakens or strengthens the relationship.

Data Analysis and Discussion

Respondent Profile: A total of 199 valid responses from respondents who completed the 32-item scale questionnaire were used for testing. The respondents consist of the young generation aged 15-30, drawn from educational institutes, and the sample includes both male and female participants who are regular consumers of SM and broadcast media

Response Pattern: Out of the distributed questionnaires, 199 complete responses were received and considered suitable for analysis. This response rate was sufficient for regression-based analysis and moderation testing at the MS level.

Treating the Missing Data / Data Cleaning: The data was examined for missing values and outliers. Missing values were minimal and were addressed using deletion.

Descriptive Statistics: This includes the mean and standard deviation calculated for all variables. The results indicated a moderate level of misinformation exposure and disengagement, with observable variation across respondents.

Descriptive statistics were calculated to summarize the central tendencies and dispersion of the research variable. As shown in Table 4.1, the mean value of all the variable fall above the midpoint of the five-point Likert scale, indicating moderate to high levels of perceived misinformation, credibility, media literacy and disengagement among respondents

Table 1: Descriptive Statistics

	N	Minimum	Maximum	Mean	Std. Deviation
MeanMisinformationOnSocialMediaIV	199	1.00	5.00	3.5232	.86789
MeanPerceivedCredibilityOfBroadcastMediaMediator	199	1.00	5.00	3.3957	.86646
MeanMediaLiteracyModerator	199	1.00	5.00	3.5754	.84945
MeanYouthDisengagementfromBroadcastMediaDV	199	1.00	5.00	3.5336	.91214
Valid N (listwise)	199				

Factor Analysis.

Exploratory factor analysis was conducted to assess the construct validity of the self-developed measurement scale. The Kaiser-Meyer-Olkin (KMO) measure of sampling sufficiency and Bartlett’s test of sphericity were used to determine the suitability of the data for factor analysis, as shown in Table 4.2. The KMO value was 0.856, indicating excellent sampling capability. Bartlett’s test of Sphericity was statistically significant ($X^2 = 3069.160$, $df = 496$, $p < .001$), confirming that the correlation matrix was suitable for factor extraction. All items were loaded with values higher than 0.4.

Table 2: KMO and Bartlett’s Test

Kaiser-Meyer-Olkin Measure of Sampling Adequacy.		.856
Bartlett's Test of Sphericity	Approx. Chi-Square	3069.160
	df	496
	Sig.	.000

Table 3: Rotated Component Matrix

	Components			
	1	2	3	4
I often come across news on social media that later turns out to be false or inaccurate.				0.730
I frequently see posts on social media that appear misleading or exaggerated.				0.705
I find it difficult to verify whether the news I see on social media is true.				0.650
Social media exposes me to conflicting information that confuses me.				0.613
I encounter emotionally charged posts that seem designed to mislead users.				0.519
I sometimes believe information on social media before checking if it is credible.				0.602
I notice that fake or unverified news spreads very quickly on social media platforms.				0.688
I feel overwhelmed by the amount of unreliable information circulating on social media.				0.626
I believe broadcast media usually provide accurate and reliable news.		0.651		
I trust broadcast media more than social media for verified information.		0.759		
Broadcast news organizations follow professional reporting standards.		0.691		
Broadcast media present news in a fair and unbiased manner.		0.715		
I consider broadcast media to be a trustworthy source of information.		0.795		
The information on broadcast channels is generally fact-checked before airing.		0.765		
Broadcast journalists are more responsible compared to social media influencers.		0.672		
When in doubt, I prefer to rely on broadcast media for the correct version of events.		0.669		
I can identify when online news is biased or misleading.			0.510	
I carefully evaluate the source before believing information on social media.			0.715	
I can differentiate between reliable and unreliable news sources online.			0.738	
I understand how social media algorithms influence the content I see.			0.679	
I verify information from multiple sources before accepting it as true.			0.806	
I can recognize when images or videos online have been manipulated.			0.597	
I know how to check the authenticity of news using fact-checking tools or websites.			0.754	
I think critically before sharing any news or information online.			0.637	
I rarely watch or listen to broadcast news anymore.	0.631			
I find broadcast media less interesting than content on social media.	0.781			
I feel disconnected from the topics discussed on broadcast news channels.	0.708			
I prefer to rely on social media for updates instead of broadcast media.	0.699			
I do not feel motivated to follow the news through television or radio.	0.794			
Broadcast media feel outdated compared to digital platforms.	0.713			
I often ignore or skip broadcast news, even when it is available.	0.726			
I believe broadcast media is becoming less relevant for people my age.	0.744			
Extraction Method: Principal Component Analysis.				
Rotation Method: Varimax with Kaiser Normalization. ^a				

Correlation Analysis: Correlation analysis was conducted to examine the relationships between the research variable. The results indicate that:

Misinformation on SM is significantly and positively correlated with the perceived credibility of broadcast media ($r = .416, p < 0.01$), media literacy ($r = .411, p < 0.01$), and youth disengagement from broadcast media ($r = .342, p < 0.01$)

A significant positive correlation was also found among perceived credibility of broadcast media and media literacy ($r = .306, p < 0.01$) and youth disengagement from broadcast media ($r = .342, p < 0.01$).

Media literacy demonstrates a significant positive correlation with youth disengagement from broadcast media ($r = .376, p < 0.01$). Overall, the results show that while misinformation is associated with all key variables, the perceived credibility alone does not have a direct bivariate relationship with youth disengagement.

Table 4: Correlations

	Misinformation	Perceived Credibility	Media Literacy	Youth Disengagement
Misinformation	1			
Perceived Credibility	.416**	1		
Media Literacy	.411**	.306**	1	
Youth Disengagement	.342**	.067	.376**	1

** . Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).

Regression Analysis

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Multiple regression analysis was conducted to test the direct and interaction effects

Model 1: Misinformation significantly predicts youth disengagement ($\beta = .342, p < 0.001$) explaining 11.7 % of the variance ($R^2 = 0.117$)

Model 2: Adding media literacy increases the explained variance to 18.4% ($R^2 = 0.184$). both misinformation ($\beta = 0.226, p = 0.002$) and media literacy ($\beta = 0.283, p < 0.001$) significantly predict disengagement.

Model 3: The interaction term between misinformation and media literacy is statistically significant ($\beta = 0.940, p = 0.006$), indicating a **moderating effect**. The model explains 21.5% of the variance in youth disengagement

Model Summary

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate	R Square Change	Change Statistics			Sig. F Change
						F Change	df1	df2	
1	.342 ^a	.117	.113	.85915	.117	26.177	1	197	<.001
2	.429 ^b	.184	.176	.82815	.067	16.027	1	196	<.001
3	.464 ^c	.215	.203	.81415	.031	7.798	1	195	.006

a. Predictors: (Constant), MeanIV

b. Predictors: (Constant), MeanIV, MeanModerator

c. Predictors: (Constant), MeanIV, MeanModerator, IntractionMeanIVModerator

Coefficients^a

Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.
		B	Std. Error	Beta		
1	(Constant)	2.265	.255		8.876	<.001
	MeanIV	.360	.070	.342	5.116	<.001
2	(Constant)	1.609	.296		5.443	<.001
	MeanIV	.237	.074	.226	3.191	.002
	MeanModerator	.304	.076	.283	4.003	<.001
3	(Constant)	-.339	.756		-.449	.654
	MeanIV	.837	.227	.797	3.690	<.001
	MeanModerator	.871	.216	.811	4.028	<.001
	IntractionMeanIVModerator	-.170	.061	-.940	-2.793	.006

a. Dependent Variable: MeanDV

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Results and Findings.

Hypothesis Testing.

The results indicated that the misinformation directly increases the youth disengagement. Media literacy significantly moderates this relationship, reducing the negative impact of misinformation.

However, the perceived credibility of broadcast media does not significantly mediate the relationship.

Comparison with Previous Studies: The finding mostly goes with the previous research highlight the influence of misinformation and the protective role of media literacy, through the mediating role of credibility, which was not statistically confirmed.

Summary of Findings: The hypothesis testing results indicated that three out of five hypotheses are supported. Misinformation on SM is found to have a significant effect on both the perceived credibility of broadcast media and youth disengagement from broadcast media. Media literacy also significantly moderated the relationship between misinformation and

disengagement. However, the perceived credibility did not have a significant direct effect on youth disengagement, and its mediating role was not supported

Table 5: Summary of Hypothesis Testing

HYPOTHESIS	RELATIONSHIP TESTED	VALUES	RESULTS
H1	Misinformation → Youth Disengagement	$r = .342, p < .01$	Supported
H2	Misinformation → Perceived Credibility	$r = .416, p < .01$	Supported
H3	Perceived Credibility → Youth Disengagement	$r = .067, p > .05$	Not Supported
H4	Mediation of Perceived Credibility	Indirect effect insignificant	Not Supported
H5	Moderation of Media Literacy	Interaction $p = .006$	Supported

Conclusion and Recommendations.

This section summarizes the key findings extracted from data analysis and presents the conclusions and recommendations. Highlight the offering of the study to the already present body of knowledge and provide practical recommendations for researchers, policymakers, media outlets and the target audience.

Overview of the study: This research study examined the impact of misinformation on SM on youth disengagement from broadcast media, with specific attention to the role of perceived credibility of broadcast media and media literacy. This study offers a new perspective by empirically testing how media literacy and credibility change the behaviour of youth and shape disengagement patterns. The research finding shows that misinformation does not work in isolation; it affects differently depending on the audience's media literacy level, which offers more understanding of the problem.

Important Findings: Results indicate that the misinformation on SM has a significant positive effect on the youth's disengagement from broadcast media. Shows that misinformation on SM significantly impact perceived credibility of broadcast media.

The perceived credibility of broadcast media did not show a significant direct relationship with youth disengagement. It shows that perceived credibility does not mediate the relationship between misinformation and youth disengagement from broadcast media. Results demonstrate

that media literacy significantly moderates the relationship between misinformation on SM and youth disengagement from broadcast media.

Contribution to the body of knowledge

This research contributes to the body of knowledge by empirically validating a moderated framework that shows the youth's disengagement from broadcast media. Results demonstrate a statistically significant relationship between misinformation, media literacy, and disengagement, supported by the correlation, coefficients, beta value and significance levels obtained through regression analysis. Media literacy works as a Moderator rather than a direct predictor. Figure 5.1 visually summarizes the empirically validated relationship between the research variables, including significant direct and interaction effects.

Figure 2: The Model of Media Literacy for Credibility of the Broadcast

Conclusion: This research study concludes that misinformation on SM is a main factor contributing to the young generation's disengagement from broadcast media. However, misinformation affects the perceived credibility; credibility alone does not directly lead to disengagement. Media literacy appears as a crucial moderating variable, showing the importance of critical media skills in shaping media usage behavior. Overall, the results underscore the complex and conditional nature of misinformation effects in the new digital era.

Recommendations and Suggestions: For future research, the researcher should consider integrating additional variables such as trust in digital platforms, emotional engagement and algorithmic awareness, which are not included in this study. They can also employ longitudinal designs to investigate changes in disengagement over time and use large or more diverse samples to increase the generalizability. Qualitative or mixed-method approaches could further enhance the understanding of youth media behavior.

Policy makers can start the media literacy initiative by incorporating critical news evaluation skills into the academic courses. Regulatory bodies can consider policies which restrict the spread of false information on digital platforms through transparency and accountability measures.

Broadcast media organizations should increase their investment in credibility-building approaches, including transparent reporting without the influence of government bias narrative, youth-oriented content formats and digital engagement ventures. Media organizations and their managers should collaborate with educational institutes and fact-checking organizations to rebuild trust among youth audiences.

References

- Abbasi, N. A. (2020). Digital Media Literacy: Social Media Use for News Consumption among Teenagers in Pakistan. *Global Media Journal*, 18, 35:210.
- Bryman, A. (2016). *Social Research Method* (5th ed.). Oxford, UK: Oxford University Press.
- Creswell, J. W. C., J. David. (2018). *Research Design: Qualitative, Quantitative, and Mixed Methods Approaches* (5th ed.). Thousand Oaks, CA: Sage Publications.
- Diaz Ruiz, C. (2023). Disinformation on digital media platforms: A market-shaping approach. *New Media & Society*, 27(4), 2188-2211.
- Ehrlén, V., Talvitie-Lamberg, K., Salonen, M., Koivula, M., Villi, M., & Uskali, T. (2023). Confusing Content, Platforms, and Data: Young Adults and Trust in News Media. *Media and Communication*, 11(4).
- Krejcie, R. V., & Morgan, D. W. (1970). Determining Sample Size for Research Activities. *Educational and Psychological Measurement*, 30(3), 607-610.
- Schulz, A., Fletcher, R., & Nielsen, R. K. (2022). The role of news media knowledge for how people use social media for news in five countries. *New Media & Society*, 26(7), 4056-4077.
- Selnes, F. N. (2023). Fake news on social media: Understanding teens' (Dis)engagement with news. *Media, Culture & Society*, 46(2), 376-392.
- Till, C. (2020). Propaganda through 'reflexive control' and the mediated construction of reality. *New Media & Society*, 23(6), 1362-1378.
- Wendt, R., Naderer, B., Bachl, M., & Rieger, D. (2023). Social Media Literacy Among Adolescents and Young Adults: Results From a Cross-Country Validation Study. *Social Media + Society*, 9(4).